

Toward More Usable, Reproducible, and Sustainable Scientific Software

The Impact of User-Centered Design in Research Software Development

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Abstract

Integrating user-centered approaches and methodologies is essential for advancing usability, reproducibility, and sustainability in scientific software. Scientific tools often prioritize technical functionality, however, creating barriers to adoption and workflow integration, especially in interdisciplinary collaborations where research and software development teams may not share the same technical background as domain scientists and end users.

At the National Center for Supercomputing Applications at the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, and specifically as a part of the Molecule Maker Lab Institute, we address these challenges by embedding user-centered design into the development of chemistry-focused, open-source software. Through case studies from the AlphaSynthesis suite, we demonstrate how methodologies such as user discovery sessions, iterative design, and usability testing can be used to address domain scientist needs and workflows. Consistent design systems and interaction patterns enhance reproducibility, allowing scientists to replicate results and workflows effectively, while scalable components and community engagement strategies promote sustainability and long-term adaptability within the research ecosystem.

This paper highlights the role of user-centered design in bridging the gap between computer science and domain science, advocating for its broader adoption within the research software development space to create impactful, enduring tools for interdisciplinary collaboration and innovation.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Interaction design**; **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Software and its engineering** → **Designing software**.

Keywords

User experience, User interface, Usability, Reproducibility, Sustainability

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1 Introduction

Scientific software is an indispensable tool in today's research landscape, but its design often ignores user needs, affecting the efficiency of researchers and the reliability of research results. Traditional development models often focus on technical functionality and ignore the actual needs of users. Despite these tools' technical advances, many face significant usability challenges, making them difficult to adopt. These problems often stem from the mismatch between tool design and user workflow, resulting in complex interfaces, steep learning curves, and difficult-to-operate features [3, 7, 12]. Addressing these challenges is critical, especially in interdisciplinary research, where diverse expertise demands intuitive and accessible design.

This paper explores how applying user-centered design (UCD) principles in software development can enhance scientific software's usability, reproducibility, and sustainability. We begin by introducing foundational concepts in user interface (UI) and user experience (UX) design, as well as related UCD framework models. We then move into the research and scientific context for our work, in particular providing an overview of AlphaSynthesis, a cross-disciplinary research effort and software suite that leverages artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) to advance chemical and molecular research and discovery. The core of this paper examines three impact areas of UCD in scientific software—usability, reproducibility, and sustainability—through case studies of AlphaSynthesis tools. These examples demonstrate how consistent design systems, scalable features, and user-focused workflows transform complex technologies into accessible, impactful software for domain scientists.

Finally, we reflect on limitations, including the need for broader user feedback and improved interoperability, and propose future directions of work. Overall, the examples from the AlphaSynthesis suite demonstrate how UCD principles can be embedded into scientific software development to create effective, reproducible, and sustainable tools that advance innovation and foster interdisciplinary collaboration.

2 Related Work

The integration of user-centered methodologies in scientific software development is grounded in well-established principles and practices of UX design and related approaches. This section identifies key definitions, models, and processes from these disciplines, providing the theoretical foundation and context for the case studies explored later in this paper.

UCD is a broad term that encompasses a number of related ideas. UX is commonly understood to encompass all aspects of an end user’s interaction with a company, its services, and its products. Ideally, a good UX should be meaningful and relevant, and have a positive emotional impact [10]. In the context of UI, which incorporates visual elements such as layout, hierarchy, and interactive components, this translates into creating designs that are usable, accessible, intuitive, and efficient. A useful analogy is posed by web developer Dain Miller:

“UI is the saddle, the stirrups, & the reins. UX is the feeling you get being able to ride the horse.”[11]

Without the proper equipment and setup, riding a horse is a painful experience. Similarly, good UI design creates and supports good UX. Here, UCD refers to the process of creating research software that meets user needs and facilitates a positive UX.

There are several well-established models and processes in the sphere of UCD on which we base our work. One foundational framework is *design thinking*. This approach asserts that user-centered problem solving can lead to innovation, and innovation can lead to differentiation and a competitive advantage. It is characterized by a cycle of six phases: (1) **Empathize**, where research is conducted to understand users; (2) **Define**, where user insights guide the formation of problems to be addressed; (3) **Ideate**, where a variety of ideas and solutions are generated; (4) **Prototype**, where these ideas are translated into tangible, interactive representations; (5) **Test**, where user feedback is gathered to improve the prototype; and (6) **Implement**, where the refined solution is developed and delivered [4].

Another common framework for UCD is the *double diamond* process, which relies on user input and feedback to evaluate and iterate on potential solutions and, ultimately, ensure a design direction that will best serve the end user. It includes four phases: (1) **Discover**, where the problem space is explored through user research and insights; (2) **Define**, where findings from the discovery phase are synthesized to define the core design challenge; (3) **Develop**, where multiple potential solutions are explored, incorporating user input and feedback; and (4) **Deliver**, where solutions are tested in order to identify and refine the most effective option for implementation [16].

While multiple representations of the UCD process exist, these frameworks underscore the importance of deeply understanding the problems users face, iteratively exploring solutions to address specific user needs, and engaging users throughout. Unfortunately, while such practices are commonly integrated into consumer and commercial software lifecycles, the same cannot be said of research software [2, 7]. This results in tools with significant challenges in usability, reproducibility, and sustainability [3, 12]. To overcome

these difficulties, we advocate for the inclusion of UCD in the scientific software – an approach we will demonstrate through our work on various tools within AlphaSynthesis.

3 Research and Scientific Context

AlphaSynthesis is an open-source software suite developed within the Molecule Maker Lab Institute (MMLI), a pioneering initiative led by the University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign (UIUC), Penn State University, and Rochester Institute of Technology. MMLI is dedicated to accelerating, advancing, and democratizing chemical and molecular research and discovery through AI and ML advancements. AlphaSynthesis plays a key role in this vision by streamlining chemical workflows through AI-guided synthesis planning, catalyst discovery, process optimization, and closed-loop discovery science.

A critical factor in ensuring AlphaSynthesis effectively serves the chemistry research community is UCD. Our design team is embedded within the AlphaSynthesis effort, collaborating closely with AI and ML researchers to align software solutions with chemistry domain user needs and workflows. By applying structured UX methodologies, we enhance the usability and impact of these tools in real-world research settings.

Beyond AlphaSynthesis, our design team is part of the National Center for Supercomputing Applications (NCSA), a leading hub for advanced computational research and interdisciplinary collaboration. Since 2020, our team has grown from a single designer to a dedicated user interface and experience (UIX) group of five full-time practitioners within NCSA. Since its official formation in 2021, the UIX team has contributed to more than 30 software projects, with applications across a wide range of domains, from molecular chemistry and genomics to climate modeling and data visualization.

Our UIX team has developed a structured design process, illustrated in Figure 1, which guides our approach and collaborations. Based on well-established frameworks and methodologies – such as those noted in the previous section – and informed by our experiences at NCSA, this process consists of three core phases: (1) **Discovery**, where we conduct domain research and engage stakeholders and users to understand goals and workflows; (2) **Ideation**, where we develop task flows, wireframes, and prototypes to iteratively explore solutions informed by usability testing; and (3) **Implementation**, where we work closely with research software engineers throughout development as designs and interactions are translated into a complete software solution.

4 Impact Areas in Scientific Software

In the following section, we will explore three areas of impact – usability, reproducibility, and sustainability – of the application of UCD to scientific software, sharing examples and case studies from our work on AlphaSynthesis tools.

4.1 Usability

Usability centers on how easily and effectively users can perform tasks, emphasizing intuitive interfaces, straightforward features, and minimal learning curves. Jakob Nielsen, a pioneer in the field of UX, defines usability as encompassing learnability, efficiency,

Figure 1: Our UIX design process incorporates various methodologies across three core phases.

memorability, error recovery, and satisfaction – all principles vital to enhancing productivity [9]. For scientific software, usability is essential for reducing the barrier to entry, minimizing errors, and empowering researchers to focus on their scientific objectives instead of on how to use the tool itself.

However, scientific software often faces usability challenges because of the inherent complexity of its subject matter and applications. Interfaces can feel difficult to navigate and have a steep learning curve, distracting users from their primary tasks. Additionally, inconsistencies in visual style and interaction logic can disrupt user workflows, resulting in a less intuitive and more unpredictable experience. This problem is exacerbated by the diversity of the potential user bases, which may include scientists, researchers, and engineers, with varying areas of technical expertise and goals when using the software. Accommodating such wide audiences can be a major obstacle in creating effective software solutions.

Our UCD approach addresses these challenges by focusing on meeting user needs through ongoing feedback and iteration. The following two case studies will demonstrate how this approach can play a powerful role in real-world projects to help bridge the gap between computer science and domain science, ensuring that software is usable and valuable to users.

4.1.1 Case Study: Somn. Somn, part of the AlphaSynthesis suite, is a predictive tool designed to accelerate workflows for C-N coupling reactions, a process that is widely used in pharmaceutical research

and manufacturing [14].¹ Traditionally, chemists have relied on conducting a series of experiments—called an experimental campaign—in order to identify the optimal conditions at which to carry out such reactions. During a campaign, various combinations of reaction conditions are surveyed, making the process time-intensive and resource-heavy [13]. Somn streamlines this workflow by helping users to efficiently predict useful conditions for their specific coupling reaction, bypassing the campaign process.

Our process for this tool began with an extensive discovery phase,² involving close collaboration with the ML research team responsible for producing an early command line version of the tool.³ Their initial goal for this project was to replicate the existing workflow in a graphical interface that would be accessible to a broader, less code-oriented user base. To build up our own baseline domain knowledge for the project, we conducted literature and code repository reviews, as well as competitive and comparative analyses of related tools. These activities informed the creation of task diagrams, user need statements, and wireframes, laying the groundwork for iterative design.

¹The Somn web interface tool is publicly available through MML: <https://somm.platform.moleculemaker.org/home>

²See the “Discovery” phase of Figure 1.

³The Somn command line tool is publicly available through GitHub: https://github.com/SEDenmarkLab/Lucid_Somnambulist

Figure 2: The Somn MVP result page incorporates familiar molecule structures and interactive data visualizations to support efficient user exploration of model results.

We centered our user discovery sessions with key user groups around these early design ideas and assets, gaining additional insights into workflows and feature concepts that shaped the development of our first release: a minimum viable product (MVP). A term commonly used in industry product development, MVP refers to a product that works from start to finish but is limited in scope and features—including what users need to complete a core workflow, but perhaps not all possible user workflows [6]. MVPs are deployed with the purpose of providing users with essential features while also creating opportunities to learn from early user feedback and ultimately increase value in future states of the solution [15]. For Somn, the MVP release prioritized workflows for one key user group:

experimental chemists focused on the targeted analysis of a single or small set of reactant pairs. At the same time, this approach laid the foundation for better supporting broader functionality and other user groups in future iterations.

Enhancing Somn’s usability beyond the original vision of the research team, we created designs⁴ that would incorporate the display of molecule structures, with which we found users to be more universally familiar than the original SMILES string requirement of the early command line solution. We also designed an interactive yield percentage density plot visualization for rapid assessment of reaction condition viability, and implemented onboarding resources, such as tutorials and contextual examples, to support user

⁴See the “Ideation and Design” phase of Figure 1.

Figure 3: The ideation phase for novoStoic 2.0 included iterative design exploration of a variety of elements, such as molecule and reaction formats, and establishing visual hierarchy in complex tabular displays.

adoption. In addition, creating a focused product scope created the flexibility to address technical constraints as they arose during implementation,⁵ such as incorporating the use of modals to manage ambiguous inputs like stereochemistry. Figure 2 shows an example result page from the Somn MVP.

Through an iterative, user-centered approach, Somn evolved from its initial command line state into a more usable, accessible, and impactful chemistry software resource.

4.1.2 Case Study: novoStoic 2.0. novoStoic 2.0 is another web-based application within the AlphaSynthesis suite, designed to support metabolic researchers and engineers in exploring biosynthesis pathways.⁶ It integrates four advanced technologies—estimating overall stoichiometry, designing de novo pathways, assessing thermodynamic feasibility, and selecting enzymes—to support the entire biosynthesis planning workflow [18]. Unlike other existing solutions that lack such integration and have limited predictive capabilities for database-missing molecules, novoStoic 2.0 provides a unified solution that improves pathway design efficiency and enables the discovery of novel biosynthetic routes.

The discovery phase⁷ for novoStoic 2.0 focused on bridging cutting-edge computational tools with user needs. Since the research team had already developed a prototype using Streamlit⁸ a Python framework for rapidly building interactive web applications, we first analyzed it to identify the tool’s key features, technical requirements, and user workflows. In addition to secondary research, we conducted consulting sessions and interviews with domain experts, leveraging the existing prototype to gather feedback on the technology, build basic knowledge of the field, and identify common user behaviors and pain points, to guide our usability improvements.

Through these sessions we found that users have varying levels of expertise and familiarity with molecular representation systems. The initial Streamlit prototype exclusively utilized KEGG ID numbers, a metabolic database standard [18], which posed a barrier for less experienced users to intuitively interpret. This issue revealed a design challenge: how might we present this unfamiliar data in a way that a wider audience can easily understand, while maintaining a seamless flow within the tool?

To address this, we took an iterative design approach to generate a range of ideas,⁹ exploring different ways to present information in wireframes. This involved collaborating with stakeholders and users to generate and evaluate various design solutions, through rapid prototyping, heuristic evaluations, and usability testing.

We explored support for alternative input formats such as common names, SMILES strings, and MetaNetX IDs, as well as ways to supplement KEGG IDs with molecular images to enhance identification. We also investigated how to access additional information more efficiently, such as through hover interactions or by expanding table rows for a more detailed view. In addition, given the complexity of the tabular content, we investigated how to reduce visual clutter caused by repeated and secondary information, establishing information hierarchies to highlight key decision data, and enabling users to access information more efficiently. Figure 3 demonstrates a variety of examples from this iterative design exploration.

Building on these user research findings and design explorations and iterations, the implemented¹⁰ novoStoic 2.0 web tool is now able to support multiple input formats. Users can also verify input accuracy through real-time molecular structure visualizations. In order to reduce visual complexity and guide users to focus on key information, not all molecules are displayed as molecular structures by default, as shown in Figure 4. User-input starting and target molecule information is fixed in specific locations and represented as colored dots in an expandable table, with hoverable details. Simultaneously, following visual hierarchy principles, bolded and

⁵See the “Implementation” phase of Figure 1.

⁶The novoStoic 2.0 web interface tool is publicly available through MML: <https://novostoitc.platform.moleculemaker.org/home>

⁷See the “Discovery” phase of Figure 1.

⁸The novoStoic 2.0 streamlit tool and command line tool are publicly available through GitHub: <https://github.com/maranasgroup/novoStoic2.0>

⁹See the “Ideation and Design” phase of Figure 1.

¹⁰See the “Implementation” phase of Figure 1.

The screenshot shows the novoStoic 2.0 interface. At the top, it identifies the user as 'AlphaSynthesis' and the tool as 'Retrobiosynthesis Pathway Design Tool with Thermodynamic Considerations and Enzyme Selection'. The job ID is 'Porttitor dui odio lacus massa' and the submission time is '01/11/2024 19:10'. The 'Input' section shows a primary precursor 'Pyruvate' (SMILES: CC(=O)C(=O)O, KEGG ID: C00022) and a target molecule '3-Hydroxypropionic acid' (SMILES: O=C(O)CCO, KEGG ID: C01013). The 'Results' section is a table of cofactors:

Overall Stoichiometry	Yield	ΔG	Actions
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 1.5 NAD ⁺ + 2.0 Water	3.0 mol	-110 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH	3.0 mol	-108 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 NAD ⁺	2.5 mol	-90 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 NAD ⁺	2.5 mol	-80 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 2.0 AMP + 2.0 diphosphate + 2.0 3,4-methyle...	2.3 mol	-20 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 4.0 phosphate + 1.0 AMP + 2.5 diphosphate + 2.0 ATP + 2.5 H ₂ O	2.3 mol	-20 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 2.0 AMP + 2.0 diphosphate + 2.0 3,4-methyle...	2.3 mol	+50 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 2.0 AMP + 2.0 diphosphate + 2.0 3,4-methyle...	2.0 mol	+80 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 2.0 AMP + 2.0 diphosphate + 2.0 3,4-methyle...	2.0 mol	+80 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →
+ 1.0 NADH + 2.0 CO ₂ + 2.0 AMP + 2.0 diphosphate + 2.0 3,4-methyle...	2.0 mol	+80 kJ/mol	Pathway Design →

A hoverable detail for 3-Hydroxypropionic acid is shown at the bottom right, displaying its chemical structure and identifying information: Common Name: 3-Hydroxypropionic acid, SMILES: O=C(O)CCO, KEGG ID: C01013.

Figure 4: The novoStoic 2.0 result page reduces visual complexity by displaying common cofactors as common names and chemical formulas, with additional information such as molecule structures available in hoverable details.

larger fonts highlight theoretical yields and Gibbs energy changes, enabling users to quickly identify pathways that meet their criteria.

Leveraging this structured and iterative design process, novoStoic 2.0 addresses challenges and user needs identified from its initial prototype and, as a result, has transformed into a refined, user-centered solution that provides an integrated and efficient platform for researchers to explore biosynthetic pathways.

4.2 Reproducibility

While reproducibility in scientific research is widely recognized as crucial to advancing knowledge and technical capabilities, a reproducibility crisis has been identified across various domains, indicating significant challenges in this area [8]. Studies show that the inability to reproduce results often stems from issues such as

insufficient documentation of methods, inaccessible data and code, selective reporting, and publication pressures. For example, a 2016 survey published in Nature found that over 70% of researchers had failed to replicate another scientist's experiment, with over 50% being unable to reproduce their own results [1].

These findings underscore the need for reproducibility-enhancing practices in scientific software development. In AlphaSynthesis tools, integrating UCD principles is a critical factor in supporting reproducible software, workflows, and, ultimately, science.

4.2.1 Reproducible Software. In the context of software design and development, the concept of reproducibility can be extended to the ability to create consistent code and user experiences across time and platforms. One key strategy our team has employed to support

Somn . Predicting substrate-adaptive conditions for C-N couplings

Request Configuration | Model Results

Job ID: 2703a57f4f434f1f9bc967c6b3bd060d

Reactant Pair Name: Example_Reactant_Pair | Submission Time: 11/25/24, 12:27 PM

Request Options | Export

Reactants		Top Predictions	
Aryl Halide	Name test1	Top Yield %	74% (1 condition)
	SMILES BrC1=NC=CC=C1	Top Reaction Conditions	RockPho K ₂ CO ₃ tAmOH
Reaction Site	Auto detected		
Amine	Name test2		
	SMILES NC1=CC=CC=C1		
Reaction Site	Auto detected		

(a) Somn results page

ACERetro . Asynchronous ChemoEnzymatic Retrosynthesis planning

Request Configuration | Model Results

Job ID: afe314b0a79e407cb5e65eddb3598c51

Max Depth: 7 | Calculating time: 600s | Submission Time: 11/25/24, 12:35 PM

Request Options | Export

Input Target Molecule

	Name	D-ribose 1-phosphate
	SMILES	O=C(COP(=O)(O)O)[C@H](O)[C@H](O)CO
	SP Score	[0.432 , 0.615]

What is SP score?
It is Synthetic Potential Scoring Function. **SPScore_Chem** and **SPScore_Bio** are metrics that assess the synthetic potential of a molecule in chemocatalysis and biocatalysis, respectively. Scores range from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a greater likelihood that the molecule can be synthesized via the respective catalytic method.

(b) ACERetro results page

Figure 5: Visual and interactive consistency across the AlphaSynthesis suite, such as the export functionality and navigation in Somn (a) and ACERetro (b), enhance familiarity and reduce cognitive load for users.

this is the adoption and expansion of standardized design systems and component libraries. Design systems integrate pre-built components and styling guidelines, creating a common language between designers and developers and facilitating a more efficient handoff between contributors. Our team leverages the PrimeNG¹¹ design system for AlphaSynthesis tools, due to its extensive library of components capable of handling large datasets and complex filtering – an important requirement for many data-intensive software projects. For design and implementation alike,¹² elements from this base component set are incorporated systematically throughout each tool’s UI, helping to ensure consistency and streamlined development. As the tools evolve over time, continued use the design system also supports scalability.

Given the highly technical nature of the scientific software our team produces, however, most projects also require custom components or data visualizations. Thus, as tools are added to the AlphaSynthesis suite, we gradually augment our component library to include more robust, domain-specific components and interactions.

¹¹More information on PrimeNG can be found here: <https://primeng.org/>

¹²See the “Implementation” phase of Figure 1.

The application of this design system to each tool in the AlphaSynthesis suite ensures not only a consistent look and feel across tools within the MMLI ecosystem, but also extends predictable interactions, such as ensuring that features like “export” and “example” buttons appear in consistent locations across modules. Such uniformity reduces cognitive load for users and enables them to quickly adopt new tools without requiring extensive retraining. Figure 5 illustrates this consistency in the context of the export functionality and navigation across tools. In another example, “molecule cards”—a standardized format we have designed for displaying chemical information—also serve to enhance familiarity and ease of use across projects, as shown in Figure 6. Thus, reproducible patterns support not only the technical design and development process, but also the end users.

4.2.2 Reproducible Workflows. While each tool in the AlphaSynthesis suite addresses a particular problem in the chemistry domain, we apply a strategic and systematic approach to emphasize reproducible workflows and feature alignment between similar tools. By creating more consistent user experiences across related workflows,

Figure 6: Reproducible design patterns, such as molecule cards in Somn (a) and novoStoic 2.0 (b), have been developed and are reused across the AlphaSynthesis suite, supporting developers and end users.

users are empowered to transition fluidly and comfortably between tools within the suite.

For example, the user workflows between ChemScraper a chemical structure extraction tool for PDF,^{13,14} and ReactionMiner, a reaction condition extraction tool for PDF (currently in progress), share strong similarities. As users navigate each tool, they encounter three aligned phases: (1) users begin by inputting literature and submitting their job for analysis; (2) users explore the extraction results, finding results of interest through methods such as searching, filtering, and sorting; and (3) users leverage their results for downstream workflows through export options such as CSV.

Another pair of related tools are ACERetro^{15,16} and RTS-CESP (currently in progress), both designed for chemo-enzymatic retrosynthesis planning. While they each leverage unique prediction scores and methodologies, they likewise share a significant overlap in workflow. This enables us to align many aspects of these tools' designs, such as the pathway visualizations shown in Figure 7. Both visualizations illustrate recommended synthesis routes, incorporating analogous information such as molecule cards color-coded by role, reaction type, and criteria for evaluating each route.

4.2.3 Reproducible Science. Across all AlphaSynthesis tools, we design features to explicitly support reproducible science. These include options such as accessing previous job results, saving results of interest, adjusting parameters, and rerunning experiments. Figure 8 shows the configuration screen for novoStoic 2.0's pathway search functionality, where users can set and adjust parameters for their request. Export functionalities allow users to capture key outputs in standard formats, further supporting reproducibility across teams and tools. Workflows are broken down into intuitive,

distinct steps, often highlighted in the interface through navigation bars or progress indicators. This step-by-step representation enables users to track their job history with clear views of inputs, outputs, and settings, minimizing errors and facilitating repeatable experimentation.

Incorporating user-centered approaches into MMLI projects has demonstrated that, while reproducibility may be a scientific challenge, it is also a design opportunity. By creating consistent, transparent, and user-friendly tools, we empower researchers to focus on their scientific goals while ensuring their processes and results are robustly reproducible.

4.3 Sustainability

Sustainability in scientific software extends beyond its initial technical implementation to how well it can adapt to evolving user needs and bases, integrate with larger ecosystems, and drive equitable access to research innovation. Research software, however, is often developed with an isolated approach and limited foresight, thus encountering barriers that prevent further improvement, growth, and adoption as the software naturally develops and matures [3]. UCD guides efforts to ensure that AlphaSynthesis tools are scalable, responsive, and cohesive, within the broader mission of supporting global goals for sustainable development.

4.3.1 Lasting Impact. All AlphaSynthesis tools begin with an MVP: an initial release that prioritizes key features to support essential user workflows. The product lifecycle does not end here, however, as UCD drives strategic planning to ensure tools remain relevant and adaptable over time. One strategy we employ is the development of product roadmaps, which document the current and future states of the tool, emphasizing problems and solutions that align with the most critical user needs [5].

For example, a preliminary interface version of ReactionMiner was developed by our ML-oriented collaborators in 2023. However, user feedback and discovery sessions¹⁷ conducted with research chemists revealed a number of painpoints in the current solution

¹³The ChemScraper web interface tool is publicly available through MMLI: <https://chemscraper.platform.moleculemaker.org/configuration>

¹⁴The ChemScraper front-end code repository is publicly available through GitHub: <https://github.com/moleculemaker/chemscraper-frontend>; and the backend is available at <https://github.com/moleculemaker/mml-backend>

¹⁵The ACERetro web interface tool is publicly available through MMLI: <https://aceretro.frontend.staging.mml-i.ncsa.illinois.edu/search-routes>

¹⁶The ACERetro code repository is publicly available through MMLI: <https://github.com/Zhao-Group/ACERetro>

¹⁷See the "Discovery" phase of Figure 1.

(a) ACERetro pathway visualization

(b) RTS-CESP pathway visualization

Figure 7: The pathway visualizations in ACERetro (a) and RTS-CESP (b) reflect workflow similarities between the two tools, enabling users to evaluate recommended synthesis routes and explore molecule roles and reaction types.

Setting Re-set

Pathway search setting
Tip: More you choose, the longer it takes.

Max number of steps per pathway design Number of pathway generated

Gibbs energy predictor
Tip: You can always adjust your selection later on the result page in the filtering section.

Check the box to filter out any pathways that have thermodynamic infeasible reactions.

Enzyme selection for novel reactions \odot
Tip: More you choose, the longer it takes.

Number of enzyme candidates you want to see

Figure 8: novoStoic 2.0 incorporates parameter settings for the pathway search functionality, enabling users to adjust parameters and rerun their request under the same conditions and supporting reproducible science.

and associated opportunities to create a more robust tool that incorporates not only technical but also user requirements. From this, we have created documentation for key workflows and features—such as reaction condition analysis across multiple documents and integrating more familiar structural representations—that will better meet domain scientist needs in the future.

In a similar fashion, Somn was initially designed to support the analysis of a single reactant pair. However, as a result of our intentional approach and close attention to scalability and adaptability during design and implementation,¹⁸ it has since grown to support the batch processing of multiple reactant pairs in one job.

4.3.2 Foundations for the Future. While individual AlphaSynthesis tools provide value to users on their own, these solutions are a part of a larger vision to create a unified suite of MMLI resources for chemists to leverage across the entire research community. Already, *novoStoic 2.0* integrates four advanced technologies in one platform, and *Open Enzyme Database*, an enzymatic data and prediction platform (currently in progress) is working to combine community-driven kinetic parameter sharing with novel property and function prediction algorithms. By leveraging reusable design components, familiar workflows and interactions, and a consistent visual language, we embed consistency in each AlphaSynthesis solution. This approach not only strengthens usability and encourages adoption of individual tools but also lays the groundwork for inter-tool connections and relationships. As we build toward a more unified suite of scientific solutions, we are able to leverage existing user familiarity and trust in the MMLI ecosystem.

4.3.3 Supporting Sustainable Development Goals through Open Science. By prioritizing open access to cutting-edge scientific advancements and technology, MMLI democratizes chemical and molecular research and discovery, enabling global collaboration and capacity-building in the research community. Thus, AlphaSynthesis tools align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, including 9.5 (enhancing scientific research), 8.2 (high-value technological innovation), and 4.3 (equal access to affordable and quality education and training) [17]. Open-source initiatives foster innovation by engaging diverse contributors. For example, *Open Enzyme Database* is an inherently community-driven platform for sharing enzyme and kinetic parameter data. User-friendly web interface designs support these communities by increasing access and ensuring that solutions benefit a broad audience, from experienced professional researchers to early-career scientists and students alike. This approach advances the sustainability of software in science and underscores MMLI's role in driving equitable innovation in the research community.

5 Limitations and Future Work

In the design and development of the AlphaSynthesis suite at MMLI, we have explored the vital role that a UCD approach can play in scientific software development to improve usability, reproducibility, and sustainability.

However, some limitations of these case studies are worth noting. First, user feedback has primarily been concentrated within the

user group of MMLI, which may limit the software's broader applicability; to address this, we would like to expand our research base to incorporate input from a more diverse range of participants. Second, as the number of tools and features within the AlphaSynthesis suite grows, there is an increasing need to ensure the efficient flow of data across tools and enhance interoperability between them. This will create a more integrated ecosystem that improves UX and provides seamless support for end-to-end scientific workflows. Finally, with increasing usage, it is essential to explore more advanced mechanisms for collecting and analyzing user behavior and usage data. While we have some basic user metric tracking in place (e.g., visits, visit duration, bounce rate, actions, etc.), as well as options for users to provide direct feedback via email for each tool, more robust systems would offer valuable insights into user needs and support iterative and ongoing improvements.

Thus, future efforts should focus on the following areas: increasing the breadth and depth of user research to capture more diverse feedback; optimizing data flow management and tool interoperability to foster greater collaboration and integration within the AlphaSynthesis suite; and developing robust data collection and analytics systems to inform design decisions and guide performance enhancements. By addressing these challenges and continuously refining our approach, we believe that UCD will play an increasingly pivotal role in driving innovation and improving the adoption and effectiveness of scientific research tools at MMLI and beyond.

6 Conclusion

This paper examines how applying a UCD approach can enhance the *usability*, *reproducibility*, and *sustainability* of scientific software. Through case studies from the AlphaSynthesis suite of MMLI, we illustrate how usability challenges can be addressed by prioritizing user needs through an iterative design process, resulting in tools that improve UX and workflow efficiency. Reproducibility is strengthened by consistent design frameworks and standardized interactions across tools, enabling users to replicate experiments and adopt new tools without extensive retraining. Sustainability is achieved by creating adaptable and scalable software ecosystems that remain relevant to evolving research needs while promoting equitable access through open-source initiatives.

Looking ahead, our efforts within the AlphaSynthesis suite will be centered on gathering more robust and diverse user feedback, increasing interoperability between tools, and further developing data collection and analytics systems to enhance the UX across the entire AlphaSynthesis ecosystem. More broadly, however, we envision a future where user-centered practices are more deeply integrated within all scientific research environments. We will continue to advocate for interdisciplinary collaborations that align software design with user needs and scientific goals – both within our own research context at MMLI and UIUC, and also amongst the wider research software community, such as the United States Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE).

In closing, integrating user-centered approaches is a critical component in the path toward more usable, reproducible, and sustainable scientific software. Through user-centered methods, software can better meet user needs, support research workflows, and

¹⁸See the "Ideation and Design" and "Implementation" phases of Figure 1.

achieve long-term success. By embedding these principles into development practices, the scientific community has the opportunity to not only accelerate innovation but also ensure that the tools it creates have a lasting impact on future discoveries.

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References

- [1] Tatiana Chakravorti, Sai Dileep Koneru, and Sarah Rajtmajer. 2024. Reproducibility, Replicability, and Transparency in Research: What 430 Professors Think in Universities across the USA and India. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.08796>. arXiv preprint. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [2] Jennifer Cham and Katrina Costa. 2017. UX Design – Maximising the Value of Scientific Software in Life Science R&D. <https://www.ddw-online.com/ux-design-maximising-the-value-of-scientific-software-in-life-science-rd-1795-201708/>. Drug Discovery World. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [3] Stephen Crouch, Neil Chue Hong, Simon Hettrick, Michael Jackson, Aleksandra Pawlik, Shoaib Sufi, Les Carr, David De Roure, Carole A Goble, and Mark Parsons. 2014. The software sustainability institute: Changing research software attitudes and practices. *Computing in Science & Engineering* 15, 6 (2014), 74–80.
- [4] Sarah Gibbons. 2016. Design Thinking 101. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/design-thinking/>. Nielsen Norman Group. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [5] Sarah Gibbons. 2020. UX Roadmaps: Definitions and Components. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ux-roadmaps/>. Nielsen Norman Group. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [6] Anna Kaley and Rachel Krause. 2023. Lean UX & Agile Glossary. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/agile-glossary/#MVP>. Nielsen Norman Group. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [7] Catriona Macaulay, David Sloan, Xinyi Jiang, Paula Forbes, Scott Loynton, Jason R Swedlow, and Peter Gregor. 2009. Usability and user-centered design in scientific software development. *IEEE software* 26, 1 (2009), 96.
- [8] National Academies of Sciences. 2019. *Reproducibility and Replicability in Science*. The National Academies Press. ISBN: 978-0-309-48616-3.
- [9] Jacob Nielsen. 1994. *Usability Engineering*. Academic Press, San Diego.
- [10] Don Norman and Jakob Nielsen. 1998. The Definition of User Experience. <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/definition-user-experience/>. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [11] Tristana Oppliger. 2021. What is UX / UI Design? <https://flatironschool.com/blog/what-is-ux-ui-design/>. Flatiron School. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [12] Francisco Queiroz, Ranieri Silva, Jonah Miller, Sandor Brockhauser, and Hans Fangohr. 2017. Good usability practices in scientific software development. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1709.00111* (2017).
- [13] Ian Rinehart et al. 2023. A machine-learning tool to predict substrate-adaptive conditions for Pd-catalyzed C–N couplings. *Science* 381 (2023), 965–972. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adg2114>
- [14] Paula Ruiz-Castillo and Stephen L. Buchwald. 2016. Applications of Palladium-Catalyzed C–N Cross-Coupling Reactions. *Chemical Reviews* 116, 19 (2016), 12564–12649. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.6b00512>
- [15] Regan Stevenson, Devin Burnell, and Greg Fisher. 2024. The Minimum Viable Product (MVP): Theory and Practice. *Journal of Management* 50, 8 (2024), 3202–3231. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01492063241227154>
- [16] UK Design Council. n.d. The Double Diamond. <https://www.designcouncil.org.uk/our-resources/the-double-diamond/>. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [17] United Nations. n.d. The 17 Goals | Sustainable Development. <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>. Accessed: 2025-04-22.
- [18] Vikas Upadhyay, Mohit Anand, and Costas Maranas. 2024. novoStoic2.0: An integrated framework for pathway synthesis, thermodynamic evaluation, and enzyme selection. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.27.615368>. bioRxiv preprint. Accessed: 2025-04-22.

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